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REVIEW ARTICLE

EFFECTIVENESS OF RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR PROTECTING FRONT-LINE WORKERS FROM THE DEVASTATING IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC WITH MAJOR FOCUS ON THEIR MENTAL HEALTH CONDITIONS

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Abstract

Going to work during the COVID-19 pandemic has placed frontline workers under immense and unprecedented pressures, putting their physical, mental, and social well-being at risk. Staff under excessive or prolonged stress become more prone to frequent absences from work or reduced productivity while at work, accidents, and mistakes. In the COVID-19 pandemic, this may mean compromised quality and safety of care, breach of protocols and guidelines, increased risk of infections, and compromised capacity of the health system and emergency response teams to fight the pandemic. While frontline workers have the responsibility of caring for themselves and verbalizing their needs and concerns, many of the efforts to prevent and reduce stress and care for the mental health of frontline workers must be made by organizations, managers, and health administrators.

Key words

Frontline workers, COVID-19, mental health

ASSESSING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES

The pandemic of COVID-19 was considered a global health emergency by the World Health Organization during March 2020¹. This pandemic has hit almost 206 countries and the frontline workers (healthcare workers) are always involved in screening and treatment during this pandemic. The pandemic of COVID-19 has brought crisis management in personnel across the globe. The frontline workers are themselves not immune to the psychological sequel of COVID-19. They are more prone to the psychological consequences of the pandemic. These psychological effects occur among the front-line workers due to the excessive workloads, an increase of working hours, unavailability of personal protective equipment, the peer pressure of the media and news channel on their working scenarios, and lack of any support system towards them². Despite all these psychological consequences, the increase in infection rate among healthcare workers is the major psychological impact for deterioration of their mental health. The immediate turnabout in the role of the front-line workers towards the patients results in the nature of helplessness, frustration, adjustment issues, and discrimination among the healthcare workers³. Hence, the reports for the COVID-19 outbreak have clearly revealed that the front-line workers are at higher risk of adhering to psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, and stress during their working durations in the hospitals.

At the time of severe health crisis, the healthcare sectors are more prone to stress conditions affecting the working life of the healthcare workers. The significant increase in the number of patients has evolved to more stressful conditions on the staff with the scarcity of health resources. One of the reports has revealed that the mental health conditions of the doctors are deteriorating with rising in case of depression, anxiety, insomnia, and distress among them⁴. The emergence of these stressful conditions has resulted in various complications by the scarcity of personal protective equipment (PPE) and other related medical resources during the pandemic. Another major risk involves the increased risk of contagion for families of frontline healthcare workers. Hence, there is a need for adopting risk management strategies for protecting the mental health conditions of the front-line workers from the devastating impact of the COVID-19 pandemic.

RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR THE FRONTLINE WORKERS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Risk management strategies are adopted by the healthcare sectors for protecting the frontline workers from mental deterioration due to the COVID-19 pandemic. The insurance of emergency medical supplies is considered to be potential for public health emergency response systems⁵. The need for appropriate mental support along with the implementation of interventions and staff support measures are considered important. The healthcare organizations are evolving the development of support teams that implements psychological interventions among the frontline workers, psychological counselling, availability of shift system in the healthcare organizations for effective working hours, development of online platforms for medical assistance for the frontline workers, providing effective incentives for motivating them to work more effectively, providing effective rest and time off from work, and implementation of activities such as meditation, yoga, and exercise along with attending the motivational sessions^{6,7}. Hence, the protection of the frontline workers from the devastating impact of COVID-19 has been considered an effective tool for maintaining their mental health condition.

The WHO has also provided various information concerning reliable sources from WHO and local health authorities on case identification, infection prevention, and control (IPC) towards the COVID-19 pandemic. The maintenance of a healthy diet and appropriate rest from the working hours has been known to be effective in reducing mental illness among the frontline workers. The seeking of professional help during the time of anxiety or depression has been considered as an effective approach for improving the mental illness of the frontline workers during the pandemic. The healthcare organizations are implementing the method of rotational shifts that further maintains the working efficiency of the organization while giving appropriate rest to their healthcare workers to take care of their health. The regular monitoring of the wellbeing of the frontline workers has been initiated by some of the healthcare organizations that have resulted in analysing the psychological status of their healthcare workers along with identification of risks and emerging issues so that appropriate action is taken for their wellbeing⁸. The motivational sessions are being conducted that helps in encouraging the frontline workers to speak openly regarding their concerns to the authority. It further provides regular updates to the frontline workers regarding the working of the management towards improving their mental health. Employee assistance programs are also conducted for carrying out effective communication with other team members regarding their mental health condition and improving their well-being. Appropriate training is being provided to the healthcare workers concerning psychological care principles and psychological first aid to improve their mental health and combating the major issues of mental illness during the COVID-19 pandemic. The adoption of basic strategies for identifying the signs of distress and major implication for reducing them is being carried out by the frontline workers normalizing their

mental condition during the pandemic. The interventions such as cognitive behavioural therapy have been found to be quite effective in improving the mental conditions of the frontline workers in this devastating scenario of pandemics.

The Government is taking appropriate measures towards psychological interventions while providing support towards the improvement of mental health majorly to the frontline workers as they are more vulnerable to pandemic stress. The possible attention is being paid towards the development of infrastructures of the workplace along with the adoption of anti-contagion measures with a regular supply of PPEs and the implementation of resilience training programs for the frontline workers to improve their mental condition in this pandemic. The mental health and psychosocial support services are available for frontline workers who need them, and that they are aware that they can access services confidentially. Frontline workers need to also have access to mental health care facilities in case of crisis situations, and psychotropic medications need to be made available to them if they are needed. Extra attention should be paid to frontline workers who have pre-existing physical or mental health conditions or disabilities, who are facing challenges in their personal lives, and those who lack social support.

CONCLUSION

The promotion of preventive measures is considered important for protecting the frontline workers from the impact of COVID-19. The understanding and knowledge of improving mental health during the pandemic results in providing a safe environment for the frontline workers towards developing their professional career and helps them in combating challenges due to COVID-19.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

There are no conflicts of interest.